

N-9-Anthracylidene-*p*-Dimethylaminoaniline Complexes of Some Transition Metals

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N-9-Anthracylidene-*p*-dimethylaminoaniline has been used to isolate the complexes of Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV), Th(IV), Ni(II) and Co(II). These were characterised by elemental analysis, magnetic, conductometric, electronic spectral and I.R. spectral studies. Magnetic and electronic spectral studies have been utilised to elucidate the tetragonal distortion from regular cubic symmetry of some of these complexes.

SCHIFF bases have been widely used as complexing agents.¹⁻³ N-9-Anthracylidene-*p*-dimethylaminoaniline (abbreviated as ADAA) consists of acyl (C=O) and azomethine (CH=N-) groups in appropriate position and hence it may produce chelate compounds. It was therefore decided to isolate and characterise the chelate compounds of Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV), Th(IV), Ni(II) and Co(II). The effect of distortion from regular cubic symmetry in some complexes produced due to nitrate and thiocyanate ligands of unequal donor strengths has also been discussed.

Experimental

The method of Kronke and Gross⁴ was employed to prepare the Schiff base N-9-anthracylidene-*p*-dimethylaminoaniline by condensing 9-anthracene-glyoxal hydrate and *p*-dimethylaminoaniline in ethanolic medium, m.p. 78°C (Found : C, 81.24 ; H, 5.46 ; N, 7.84 ; requires : C, 81.80 ; H, 5.68 ; N, 7.93 ; percent).

All the metal salts TiCl₄, ZrCl₄, HfCl₄, ThCl₄, Ni(NO₃)₂, Ni(NCS)₂, Co(NO₃)₂ and Co(NCS)₂ used were of A.R. quality and their metal contents were estimated by standard methods.

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses were carried out at the Microanalytical laboratory, I.I.T. Kanpur. The conductance, magnetic and spectral studies were carried out by the reported methods¹⁻³. Electronic spectra were studied both in solid state and in solution in acetone.

Isolation of Complexes :

Coloured solutions obtained on mixing equimolar solutions of the metal salts and the ligand in ethanol in stoichiometric 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) were refluxed for 2.5-5.5 hrs on steam bath. The reaction mixtures were cooled by refrigeration for few hours to few

days and coloured crystals of the complexes were obtained which were washed with water, ethanol, ether and methylcyanide and dried in vacuum desiccator. Ethanolic solutions of Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV) and Th(IV) complexes yielded white precipitate with ethanolic silvernitrate solution indicating thereby the presence of chlorine outside the co-ordination sphere of these complexes.

Molecular weights of the complexes were determined by cryoscopic method in bromoform medium. Magnetic moments were determined in powder form on Guoy's Balance and molar conductance measurements were carried out in NM medium. Analytical data colour and physical properties of the complexes are cited in Table 1.

Results and Discussions

Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV), Th(IV), Ni(II) and Co(II) form 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complexes. All these complexes are insoluble in water but soluble in the organic solvents such as DMSO, DMF, NM, bromoform and benzene. Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes show nonelectrolytic nature⁶ whereas the other complexes exhibit biunivalent electrolytic nature⁷⁻⁸. Molecular weights were determined by cryoscopic method using bromoform as the solvent and these are in good agreement with the calculated values. The electronic spectral data in solid state and solution are identical showing thereby no change in structure of the complexes in the two states.

Magnetic Studies :

Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV) and Th(IV) complexes exhibit magnetic moments 0.11-0.28 B.M. showing thereby octahedral symmetry⁹ of the complexes. Nitrate and thiocyanate complexes of Ni(II) and Co(II) show magnetic moments 2.72, 2.69 B.M. and 3.96, 4.02 B.M. These values are slightly lower than the usual range 2.95-3.68 B.M. and 4.65-5.2 B.M. as reported

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TABLE—1. COLOUR AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	% Elemental analysis					Molar conductance		Molecular weight	
		Calcd. (Found) C	Calcd. (Found) H	Calcd. (Found) N	Calcd. (Found) Halogen	Calcd. (Found) Metal	$\lambda\text{mohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$ (in NM)	$\mu_{\text{eff}}(\text{B.M.})$	Calcd.	Found
[Ti(C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Violet	64.43 (64.00)	4.47 (4.23)	6.26 (6.10)	15.89 (15.02)	5.36 (5.18)	175	0.11	894	875
[Zr(C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Blue	61.46 (61.08)	4.26 (4.19)	5.97 (5.78)	15.16 (15.00)	9.73 (9.68)	160	0.18	937	918
[Hf(C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Pink	52.96 (52.78)	3.90 (3.75)	5.46 (5.37)	13.06 (12.82)	17.44 (17.16)	182	0.22	918	902
[Th(C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂	Violet	52.90 (52.00)	3.68 (3.59)	5.15 (5.00)	13.04 (12.96)	21.04 (20.85)	158	0.28	1078	1056
[Ni(C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Bluish Green	66.95 (66.52)	4.51 (4.40)	9.47 (9.28)	-	6.62 (6.59)	50	2.72	886.7	872
[Ni(C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O) ₂](NCS) ₂	Green	68.00 (68.00)	4.55 (4.42)	9.55 (9.36)	-	6.68 (6.59)	32	2.96	878.7	868
[Co(C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Pink	66.94 (66.49)	4.51 (4.42)	9.47 (9.51)	-	6.62 (6.56)	35	3.96	886.9	860
[Co(C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O) ₂](NSC) ₂	Violet	68.24 (68.00)	4.55 (4.46)	9.55 (9.44)	-	6.68 (6.60)	28	4.02	878.9	870

for high spin octahedral complexes of Ni(II) and Co(II). It has been possible due to the lowering of O_h symmetry, thus suggesting distortion which is further confirmed by the electronic spectral studies.

Electronic Spectral Studies :

In the electronic spectra of [Ni(C₂₄H₂₀N₂O)₂](NO₃)₂ and [Ni(C₂₄H₂₀N₂O)₂](NCS)₂ four peaks have been observed at 9600, 12550, 17400, 29000 cm⁻¹ and 8150, 12200, 15020, 26260 cm⁻¹ in solution whereas spectra in solid state exhibit peaks at 9560, 12510, 17385, 29100 cm⁻¹ and 8125, 12190, 15000, 26400 cm⁻¹ showing a close agreement. First two bands in each case may be due to the splitting of ν_1 band because of the low symmetry of the ligand field or due to spin-forbidden transition whereas the last two bands characterise O_h symmetry. Careful scrutiny of the spectra in solution state, provides the following informations that it is not a spin-forbidden transition but a low symmetry component of the ν_1 band.

(i) Calculated ν_3 and ν_8 are 16146, 1341 cm⁻¹ and 30248, 27000 cm⁻¹ respectively which differ considerably to the experimental values, showing thereby tetragonal distortion of O_h symmetry.

Corresponding experimental values of the bands are 17400, 15020 cm⁻¹ and 29000, 26200 cm⁻¹ respectively.

(ii) The ratios ν_2/ν_1 for these complexes are 1.82 and 1.82 which are greater than the usual range 1.5-1.76 as reported¹⁰ for the O_h symmetry, indicating thereby tetragonal distortion of O_h symmetry.

(iii) However, the difference of ($\nu_3-\nu_2$) calcd. and ($\nu_3-\nu_2$) obs. for octahedral symmetry is small but here this difference appears to be 6302 cm⁻¹ and 6789 cm⁻¹. This difference is comparable to tetragonally distorted octahedral complexes¹¹.

(iv) The values of B calculated for the present complexes are 1173 cm⁻¹ and 1122 cm⁻¹ which are greater than the free ion value 1080 cm⁻¹. It may be assumed due to tetragonal distortion¹² of octahedral symmetry.

On the basis of the above facts it is concluded that the bands at 12550 cm⁻¹ and 12200 cm⁻¹ as experimentally observed are the low symmetry components. Therefore, for tetragonally distorted octahedral complexes with nitrate and thiocyanate ligands co-ordinated along Z-axis, the most favourable transitions for the first two bands are ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_g$ (9600 cm⁻¹, 8150 cm⁻¹) and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$ (12550 cm⁻¹, 12200 cm⁻¹) having energies (10 D_q - $\frac{35}{4}Dt$) and 10 D_q² in terms of radial parameters. The parameter Dt directly related to tetragonal distortion comes out to be 337 cm⁻¹ and 463 cm⁻¹. The field along Z-axis is much weaker than along the xy plane as revealed by the parameters D_q(x,y), 1255 cm⁻¹, 1220 cm⁻¹ and D_q(z), 295 cm⁻¹, 405 cm⁻¹, supporting thereby the reduced values of magnetic moments.

In the electronic spectra of Co (II) complexes in solution in acetone three bands at 8400, 8050 cm⁻¹ [${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1)]; 18850, 18600 cm⁻¹ [${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2)] and 24700, 24500 cm⁻¹ [${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3)] have been observed whereas the calculated band positions (ν_2) are 19100 cm⁻¹ and 18737 cm⁻¹ respectively which are in close agreement with the experimental band positions. It may be taken as a measure of tetragonal distortion^{12,14} of O_h symmetry. Spectral bands of these two complexes in solid state appeared at 8350, 8325 cm⁻¹; 18760, 18500 cm⁻¹ which are identical to those as observed in solution state.

Splitting energy parameter (10 D^q), racah parameter B and nephelauxetic ratio β of Co (II)

complexes are 9830, 9408 cm^{-1} ; 1024, 980 cm^{-1} and 0.91, 0.87 respectively. Nephelauxetic ratio β happening due to the partial overlapping of 3d orbitals with σ and π orbitals of the ligand consists of both $f^2 \sigma$ and $f^2 \pi$ i.e. $f^2 = f^2 \sigma$, $f^2 \pi$ and are 0.91 and 0.87, showing thereby the coincidence to the values as have been observed for tetragonally distorted¹⁶ octahedral complexes of Co (II).

Infrared Spectral Studies :

IR spectra of the complexes as compared to that of the ligand show lowering of stretching frequencies of active carbonyl ($=\text{C}=\text{O}$) and azomethine ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$) groups such as 1700 cm^{-1} to 1630-1650 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} to 1520-1560 cm^{-1} respectively, indicating the formation of complexes through these groups. Appearance of bands at 425-465 cm^{-1} and 475-550 cm^{-1} indicate the formation of metal-oxygen (M-O) and metal-nitrogen (M-N) bonds, supporting thereby chelation through oxygen and nitrogen atoms. However, peaks around 325-425 cm^{-1} are observed in the IR spectra of complexes of Ti (IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV) and Th(IV), thus revealing the formation of metal-halogen (M-Cl) bonds.

The nitrate complexes of Ni (II) and Co (II) exhibit bands at 1290 cm^{-1} and 1280 cm^{-1} in their IR spectra, showing thereby that the complexes are nitrate-bonded¹⁶.

The thiocyanate complexes show stretching vibrations at 2080-2150 cm^{-1} and 690-810 cm^{-1} respectively, corresponding to $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ and C-S. However, in spectra of the present complexes bands at 2040, 2045 cm^{-1} and 800, 825 cm^{-1} are observed, indicating the co-ordination of thiocyanate ion with the metal ions through N-atom¹⁷.

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